

Homœopathy—*isopathy*

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It is sometimes suggested that homœopathy has failed to evolve, that it has stood still over the last 150 years. Yet in an age of 'disposable' medicine—with yesterday's latest and best method the malpractice of today—homœopaths take a positive view of continuity, valuing reliability. At the same time, however, homœopathy has definitely been evolving further. Homœopaths take a good look at the world of medicine and biology and adopt anything which is in accord with the teaching of Hahnemann. We can say with confidence that homœopathy is very much alive.

Examples which come to mind are nosodes such as *Diphtherinum*, *Scarlatinum*, *Pertussinum* and many others, well established in the meantime. Unknown in Hahnemann's day, they are more and more widely used today, with good results.

These potentized agents have been to some extent discredited due to misuse. Apparently there are colleagues who use them simultaneously and in such massive doses that it is impossible to speak of either homœopathy or *isopathy* in their case. This is a pity.

To help the situation, I have attempted to establish a clear distinction between nosodes and potentized toxins, between homœopathy and *isopathy*, basing myself on the many different statements, not all in agreement, that are to be found in the literature (Table 1).

NOSODES are potentized morbid products prescribed on the basis of the homœopathic principle. They include elimination products from the diseased organism (pus, sputum, skin scales etc.) as well as pure cultures of pathogens (heat-sterilized) and toxic products of these organisms.

If the eliminations or pathogens have been obtained from the patient under treatment—some authors consider these the only nosodes to be used—they are known as *autonosodes*. At this point, reference may also be made to the use of blood taken from the patient and then given in potentized form for a stimulative effect and to reduce auto-aggression (Imhaeuser).

It is not possible in this paper to consider the history of therapy with nosodes. This was known to Hippocrates and Paracelsus and continued on to Lux, the veterinary surgeon who was the first to potentize these agents. His brochure published fifty years before Robert Koch discovered bacteria bore the almost prophetic title *Isopathik der Contagionen*.

Unfortunately, no standards have yet been established in the Federal Republic for the manufacture of nosodes from starting materials which tend to present very considerable problems. In France, for instance, this has been done long since. For

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TABLE 1 Differentiation of homœopathy and isopathy

	NOSODES	TOXINS
HOMŒOPATHY	Tuberculinum Medorrhinum Psorinum Luesinum (Syphilitum) Pertussinum Diphtherinum Diphtherotoxinum Scarlatinum etc.	metals heavy metals halogens acids salts phosphorus petroleum glonoine etc.
ISOTHERAPY	Pertussinum Diphtherinum Diphtherotoxinum Scarlatinum Influenzinum Streptococcinum Staphylococcinum Enterococcinum etc.	glonoine a.o. chemicals industrial poisons environmental toxins pharmaceuticals etc.

the physician, then, it is very much a matter of individual judgement as to where to obtain one's nosodes, with different manufacturers offering different nosodes.

Potentized TOXINS represent a second large group of agents. In fact, homœopathy has always made use of toxic materials such as phosphorus, arsenic, lead and many others as well as materials of plant and animal origin. In recent times, modern chemicals, environmental toxins and chemical drugs have been added to the list. Potentized and prescribed on homœopathic principles they can be of definite benefit where indicated.

Mode of action

Both groups, nosodes and toxins, can be prescribed on homœopathic as well as isopathic principles:

- homœopathically if the drug picture has been established, using the law of similars,
- isopathically according to the principle of sameness, the principle of the causative agent.

Among the nosodes, established agents such as *Tuberculinum*, *Medorrhinum* and *Luesinum (Syphilitum)* are good examples for homœopathic use. They are used to treat not only tuberculosis, gonorrhoea or syphilis, but in syndromes presenting a picture similar to that of these diseases, i.e. according to the law of similars. Julian has established the drug pictures for more recent nosodes such as *Diphtherinum*, *Pertussinum* and others. *Pertussinum* may therefore be used on the homœopathic principle to treat pseudocroup not caused by pertussis, asthma, and chronic bronchitis with retching. *Diphtherinum* is a useful similar in many neuro-

logical conditions, particularly flaccid paralysis, when diphtheria has played no specific role in the pathogenesis. Again the use is homœopathic.

It becomes isopathic only if the drug is used to treat a condition caused by the same pathogen. The method may be used to treat residual problems when an illness has been overcome earlier in life, problems following on vaccination or toxic factors in the home or school environment, and also to reduce hereditary problems—always isopathically. Impressive case material has been presented by Dr Haas.

Both methods are also possible with the other group of agents, i.e. potentized toxins. Homœopathy has always used the law of similars, basing its prescribing on the toxicology of the agent in question. Examples are metals, including heavy metals, alkalis and alkaline earths, salts and acids, phosphorus, arsenic, creosote, terebinth and petroleum. Full drug pictures have been established for all of these, and they are prescribed if the clinical picture is similar. Nitroglycerin is an industrial poison included in the materia medica under the name of *Glonoinum*, and Julian has now also produced the drug picture for penicillin. So much concerning homœopathic use.

All these old familiars can of course also be used on the isopathic principle if they have been the causative agent. Perhaps we are not entirely aware how often we give *Plumbum* for instance as an isopathic drug when patients heavily exposed to car exhaust fumes present with a *Plumbum* picture. I feel that new potentials will increasingly open up for isotherapy in this field of environmental pollution and iatrogenic disease. From the USA we hear of 'clinical ecology' applying desensitization in brutal doses, having no knowledge or experience of isopathy. Isotherapy requires no drug picture. It is the causative agent itself that is used in high potencies and single doses at long intervals. Voisin used *Alumina* to treat workers in the aluminium industry suffering from industrial disease due to alumina, and *Cobaltum* for workers in the cobalt industry. Bier cured postanaesthetic ether bronchitis with potentized ether, etc.

The causative factor can usually be established without much trouble by careful history-taking, concentrating on the questions 'since when' and 'due to what'. An example is the girl of fifteen whose performance at school has gone down for the last few months and who has changed completely. Narcotics? No. Since when, then? Since Christmas. Due to what? She had many hours exposure to acrylic vapours when making things for Christmas, and still cannot bear the smell, as she says. Potentized acrylate cured her. One wonders if many of the victims at Seveso could not also have been helped with isopathy.

It is necessary to make clear distinction between homœopathic and isopathic use of both nosodes and potentized toxins. This is important because the mechanism of action is different for isopathy, with different therapeutic consequences.

Homœopathy acts on the basis of similarity, and the action is gentler, more broadly based and regulative. The illness is cured 'almost of its own accord'.

Isotherapy on the other hand acts through the causative factor itself. Potentization reverses the direction of action, with the result that the organic bond between toxin and body protein is broken, as shown by Madame Wurmser in her very exciting experiments. The toxin is then washed out, to an extent that can never be

foreseen. This unforeseeable toxic effect of isotherapy is best taken into account by considering the points listed in Table 2.

If isotherapy with nosodes or potentized toxins is used intelligently, with full medical knowledge and careful clinical observation, if it is used with due caution and in the context of carefully assessed general homœopathic treatment, it will in many cases give impressive results that could not have been achieved with other drugs.

TABLE 2 *Points to be considered in the practice of isotherapy*

- 1 Isopathic nosodes should never be given during the acute stage of the disease they have caused, only when the acute stage is passing or for chronic states.
 - 2 Isopathic toxins to be given only after exclusion of the causative agent.
 - 3 Isopathic nosodes and toxins are as far as possible to be given by the parenteral route (except in the case of children), as this brings out the fuller effect. Bier considered the parenteral route the fastest and most efficient, and in his view this was due to the special immunological functions of the skin.
 - 4 Nosodes or toxins should always be given singly, i.e. never the nosodes of all past illnesses together. The proper choice has to be made of the nosode responsible for the residual problems in the given situation.
 - 5 Isopathic medication should be given only at intervals. Once a week is usually sufficient, with longer intervals for higher potencies.
 - 6 Care must be taken not to go too low in potency. Experienced practitioners never go below the 30x. C and even LM potencies are advisable with highly toxic nosodes.
 - 7 Chronic conditions are best treated with rising potencies, at increasingly longer intervals.
 - 8 Isopathic therapy using nosodes and toxins should go hand in hand with carefully selected homœopathic treatment to cover the presenting symptomatology.
 - 9 Isopathy must not be used if eliminatory functions are insufficient. The French school has introduced the concept of 'drainage' remedies intended to stimulate eliminatory functions.
 - 10 Always encourage patients to take a lot of fluids during isotherapy, at least 1½ litres per day.
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